

IMPACT OF PARENTAL SUPPORT TOWARDS THE ACADEMIC ACHIEVEMENT OF PUPILS IN ARALING PANLIPUNAN

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Impact of Parental Support towards the Academic Achievement of Pupils in Araling Panlipunan

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Abstract

This study explores the impact of parental support on the academic achievement of Pupils in Araling Panlipunan. Recognizing the crucial role of parents in fostering a conducive learning environment, this research investigates how various forms of parental environment -such as providing study resources, assisting with homework, and encouraging active participation in school activities-affect pupils' performance in the subject. Using a mixed method approached, the study gathers quantitative data on academic performance and qualitative insights from pupils and their parents. Findings reveal a significant correlation between parental support and improved academic outcomes, highlighting the importance of family engagement in shaping students' learning experiences. The study concludes with practical recommendations for parents and educators to enhance collaborative efforts in supporting pupils' academic success in Araling Panlipunan.

Keywords: *Parental support, academic achievement, Araling Panlipunan, parental involvement, pupil performance, family engagement, education, student success*

Introduction

Within the Department of Education, specifically at North Dalurong Elementary School, parents exhibit varied approaches in their involvement in their children's academic success. Some people are actively involved in an activity, whereas others are not. They ignore the idea that parental involvement in children's education has been widely acknowledged as a crucial indication of pupil achievement. It has a beneficial influence on pupils' academic performance and is an essential element in tackling numerous issues in education. An effective and resilient collaboration between educational institutions and families cultivates pupils' acquisition of knowledge and amplifies the progress of schools. Consistently practicing the knowledge gained at school is crucial, even when at home. If the young individual senses a substantial level of support from his parents, it is probable that he will possess a strong motivation to actively participate in the process of acquiring knowledge and try for exceptional performance in his educational endeavors. The level of parental involvement in school events has a significant impact on pupils' enthusiasm for learning. It enhances kids' academic achievement, a vital component of effective education for school-aged children (Tatoy, 2015). Through the active involvement of parents in their children's academic experiences, they will have a thorough comprehension of their children's successes and difficulties in school. The main reason for the creation of formal home-school groups and organizations, such as the General Parents Teachers Association (GPTA), School Governing Council (SGC), and Homeroom Parents Teacher Association (HRPTA), in educational institutions is to encourage parents to actively participate in school activities. These groups exert great effort to cultivate a strong bond between the household and the realm of education. The purpose of this is to distribute resources in order to attain the objective of delivering education of superior quality. School-Based Management (SBM) establishes a mutually beneficial connection between the school and community, with a focus on the pupils' welfare as a top priority.

The aim of this study was to evaluate and reconsider the level of parental support contributing to the academic success of pupils at North Dalurong Elementary School throughout the academic year 2019-2020.

Research Questions

This study ascertained the extent of parental support towards the academic achievement of pupils in Kitaotao III District, Division of Bukidnon, SY 2019-2020. Specifically, this study aimed to answer the following questions:

1. What is the extent of parents' support towards the academic achievement of pupils in terms of parents as: Communicator, Supporter, Pupil, Advocate, Decision Maker, Volunteer, Acting as Home Teacher, and Collaborator?
2. What is the academic achievement of the pupils?
3. Is there a significant relationship between the extent of parental support towards their child and the academic achievement of their children?

Methodology

Research Design

This study utilized a descriptive-correlational research design, employing the descriptive correlation method to collect factual information and provide a precise interpretation of the findings. The goal was to identify the relationships between variables and establish the extent of parental support in relation to the academic achievements of pupils in Kitaotao III District, Division of Bukidnon, during the school year 2019-2020. A questionnaire, adapted from Galila's 2017 study, was employed to gather data on the influence of parental support on pupils' academic achievements.

Respondents

This study involved Grade VI pupils' parents from selected public elementary schools within Kitaotao III District, Division of Bukidnon, during the academic year 2019-2020. The researcher specifically chose a large school, South Dalurong I.S., with 40 respondents, a medium-sized school, Kitubo Central School, with 30 respondents, and a small school, North Dalurong E/S, with 20 respondents. The distribution of participants across the schools is detailed in Table 1.

Table 1. *Distribution of Respondents by School*

<i>School Size</i>	<i>Name of School</i>	<i>Number of Respondents</i>	<i>Total</i>
Big School	South Dalurong I.S.	40	40
Medium School	Kitubo Central School	30	30
Small School	North Dalurong E/S	20	20
Total		90	90

Respondents were selected through purposive random sampling in this study. The researcher deliberately utilized geographic sampling, specifically choosing one small school, one medium-sized school, and one large school within the Kitaotao III district.

Instrument

The research employed a survey questionnaire as its primary instrument, adapted from Galila's study, which itself drew inspiration from Rahman's work in 2001. To ensure parents' comprehension, the questionnaire was translated into the vernacular language and consisted of two sections.

In Section I, the focus was on assessing the extent of parental support for pupils' academic achievement. This assessment included dimensions such as parent as communicator, parent as supporter of school activities, parent as pupil, parent as advocate, parent as decision maker, parent as volunteer/professional, and parent as home activities teacher. Each of these areas comprised five items, and respondents utilized a Five-Point Likert Scale to indicate their chosen answers.

Section II aimed to gather information on pupils' academic achievement, specifically requiring the final grades of pupils during the school year 2019-2020. This information was obtained from the class advisers.

Procedure

Information concerning the extent of parental support for pupils' academic achievement was gathered through the completion of questionnaires distributed to the respondents. The pupils' final grades were obtained from their respective advisers, and the survey on parental support was carried out among the parents of the pupils.

The data collection process involved several steps, starting with the submission of a permission letter to the Dean of Graduate Studies for research approval. Subsequently, the permission letter was distributed to DepEd personnel, including the Schools Division Superintendent, Public Schools District Supervisor, and School Principal/School Head. The third step involved distributing questionnaires to the selected respondents, and finally, the retrieval of the questionnaires was carried out.

Data Analysis

The research utilized the following statistical methods for data analysis:

Mean and standard deviation were applied to evaluate the degree of parental support for pupils' academic achievement.

Frequency count and percentage were employed to ascertain the level of academic achievement among the pupils.

To identify any notable correlation between the extent of parental support for their children and the academic achievement of their children, the Pearson Product-Moment Correlation Coefficient (or Pearson r) was utilized.

Results and Discussion

This chapter presents the analysis and interpretation of the extent of parental support towards the academic achievement of pupils in Kitaotao III District, Division of Bukidnon, SY 2020-2021. The presentation was presented based on the order of the problems posed in Chapter I.

Extent of Parents' Support towards the Academic Achievement of pupils in terms of parents as: Communicator, Supporter, Pupil, Advocate, Decision Maker, Volunteer, and Acting as Home Teacher

Table 2 presents the data on the Extent of Parents' Support towards the Academic Achievement of pupils in terms of parents as Communicator.

The results show that parents are moderately involved (wt.mean =2.843, SD=1.214) in attending to the concerns of the school about their child's studies both academic and non-academic through (e.g., letters, phone calls or e-mails). This implies that educators in Kitaotao III District believe that effective communication, whether through letters, phone calls, texts, or messaging apps, fosters

understanding and trust. When teachers and parents have a mutual understanding and trust each other, they can collaborate more effectively to support the well-being and development of children. This highlights the crucial role of effective communication in establishing and sustaining positive partnerships with parents. Both parents and teachers share a common objective: to enhance the overall educational experience for pupils. Through communication, parents and teachers can work together to achieve this shared goal, with each party contributing their specific skills and knowledge towards fulfilling the objectives.

Table 2. *Extent of Parents’ Support towards the Academic Achievement of pupils in terms of parents as Communicator*

<i>Parent as Communicator</i>	<i>Indicators</i>	<i>Weighted Mean</i>	<i>Standard Deviation</i>	<i>Qualitative Description</i>
Isip guinikanan, ako naningkamot nga.....				
1. I receive information on what I can do at home to help my child improve or advance his/her learning. (Makabalo kung unsa akong maitabang sa akong anak didto sa among balay para mapalambo niya iyang pagtuon.)		3.056	1.393	Moderately Involved
2. I could talk with my child’s classmates and peers about how my child is behaving/doing at school. (Maka-istorya ako sa mga barkada/higala sa akong anak kung unsa ang gawi sa akong anak sa eskwelahan.)		3.367	1.378	Moderately Involved
3. I can talk openly with my child’s teachers and principal about problems that he or she may be having at school with peers, faculty, or course work. (Gawasnon ako nga maka-istorya sa mga magtutudlo ug principal bahin sa mga posibleng problema sa akong anak sa eskwelahan bahin sa mga kaeskwela, magtutudlo, o sa pagtuon mismo.)		3.444	1.407	Strongly Involved
4. I could attend to the concerns of the school about my child’s studies both academic and non-academic through(e.g., letters, phone calls or e-mails). (Nakiglambigit ako bahin sa updates sa pagtuon sa akong anak pinaagi sa sulat, telepono, o-email sa internet.)		2.843	1.214	Moderately Involved
5. I keep my communication with my child open about his/her studies, the problems, challenges, and victories. (Akong gipaningkamutan nga kanunay abli ang among kumonikasyon sa akong anak bahin sa iyang pagtuon, mga problema, mga pagsulay, ug mga kadaugan.)		3.122	1.244	Moderately Involved
	Total	3.1664	0.0786	Moderately Involved

Legend: 4.20 – 5.00 – Very Strongly Involved (VSI) | 3.40 – 4.19 – Strongly Involved (SI) | 2.60 – 3.39 – Moderately Involved (MI) | 1.80 – 2.59 – Less Involved or Never (LI) | 1.00 – 1.79 – Not Involved (NI)

However, if parents cannot attend to their child through any medium of communication but they are strongly involved (wt. mean=3.444, SD=1.407) in talking openly with their child’s teachers and principal about problems that he or she may be having at school with peers, faculty, or course work. This implies that when parents serve as communicators, teachers have the ability to openly contact and approach parents in instances where there are concerns about their child's aggressive behavior. Parents in the role of communicators offer advantages such as enhanced communication with both children and teachers. Regular updates on children's academic performance contribute valuable insights for classroom goals and strategies.

Overall, based on these results, the extent of parents’ support towards the academic achievement of pupils in terms of parents as communicator was rated as Moderately Involved (wt. mean=3.1664, SD=0.0786). Moreover, respondents have unanimous responses, there was not much deviation as shown by the SD values which are within 68% of the distribution which means the values are almost near the mean. Research suggests that when parents engage in regular communication with teachers and actively participate in school-related activities, children show improved academic performance. Furthermore, parents have a significant influence on decision-making processes that can potentially affect their child's education. Researchers have analyzed the impact of parents on the growth of both inherent and external motivation in their offspring (Deci et al., 2009). Irrespective of the nomenclature employed to describe these principles, they all center on the notion that motivation can originate either within or be supplied outside.

The Self-Determination Theory of Motivation (SDT) article explores the difficulties encountered by educators and parents in stimulating their students or children to exert greater effort in their academic assignments (Deci et al., 2009). According to the Self-Determination Theory (SDT) model, students can be influenced by two primary forms of motivation: autonomous motivation and controlled motivation. These categories consist of subcategories that are classified according to either intrinsic or extrinsic ideology. Autonomous motivation refers to engaging in an activity with genuine willingness and enthusiasm, driven by personal choice and delight. In contrast, controlled motivation refers to the act of carrying out a task due to external factors such as pressure, demands, or coercion (Deci et al., 2009). If a youngster exhibits intrinsic motivation, which refers to their engagement in a task purely because they find it rewarding or captivating, then they are displaying a type of autonomous motivation.

Table 3 presents the data on the Extent of Parents’ Support towards the Academic Achievement of pupils in terms of parents as Supporter.

As shown in Table 3, the extent of parents’ support towards the academic achievement of pupils in terms of parents as supporter revealed that the parents let their child join academic-related contests and activities(e.g. journalism, MTAP, etc.) (wt. mean=3.333,

SD=1.438) described as Moderately Involved and got the highest mean. This indicates that parents in Kitaotao III District demonstrated significant support for their children's education. Being a supportive parent involves prioritizing a child's well-being while actively participating, engaging, and providing assistance. It includes actively motivating children to excel both academically and in their personal hobbies and interests. This phenomenon stems from a deep fascination with the subject matter and a personal attachment to the acquisition of knowledge. On the other hand, students who are motivated by regulated rewards have a tendency to just memorize information without truly grasping the fundamental principles. Parents are advised to prioritize the provision of autonomous motives over regulated motivations, as this leads to more favorable and sustainable outcomes (Deci et al., 2009).

Table 3. *Extent of Parents' Support towards the Academic Achievement of pupils in terms of parents as Supporter*

<i>Parent as Supporter</i>	<i>Indicators</i>	<i>Weighted Mean</i>	<i>Standard Deviation</i>	<i>Qualitative Description</i>
Isip guinikanan, ako naningkamot nga.....				
1. I let my child join academic-related contests and activities(e.g. journalism, MTAP, etc.) (Akong ginatugotan akong anak nga moapil ug mga kalihokan nga konektado sa iyang pagtuon sama sa mga contests pananglitan, Journalism, MTAP.)		3.333	1.438	Moderately Involved
2. I regularly attend pahina, brigade eskwela, GPTA/ Homeroom meeting, PTC, and other parent-call ups. (Kanunay akong nagatambong ug pahina, brigada eskwela, GPTA/Homeroom meeting, PTC, ug uban pang pagpatawag sa guinikanan.)		3.300	1.449	Moderately Involved
3. I let my child join non-academic activities to boost his/her self-confidence and help school raise funds for the completion of their projects (kiddie king& queen, raffle, etc.) (Akong ginatugotan akong anak nga moapil ug kalihokan bisan kini walay labot sa "academic" para mapalambo niya iyang kumpiyansan sayang kaugalingon ug nga para makatigom ug pundo ang eskwelahan sama sa "Kiddie King & Queen", raffle, ug uban pa.)		3.278	1.430	Moderately Involved
4. I oftentimes help my child engage in educational activities outside of the class. (Ako kanunay nga gitabangan akong anak nga moapil sa mga kalihokan gawas sa ilang klase.)		3.144	1.434	Moderately Involved
5. I am primarily responsible for making sure that my child is supported to do his or her best in school. (Ako ang responsable sa pagsigurado nga ang akong anak suportado nga buhaton ang iyang kinakusgan nga makaya sa eskwelahan.)		2.967	1.402	Moderately Involved
	Total	3.2044	0.0117	Moderately Involved

Legend: 4.20 – 5.00 – Very Strongly Involved (VSI) | 3.40 – 4.19 – Strongly Involved (SI) | 2.60 – 3.39 – Moderately Involved (MI) | 1.80 – 2.59 – Less Involved or Never (LI) | 1.00 – 1.79 – Not Involved (NI)

Although prizes might serve as an incentive for a youngster to finish a task, they have the potential to decrease their intrinsic interest in the activity. Hence, if a youngster's inclination to excel in academics is exclusively dependent on a system of rewards or punishments, the child may be likely to cease engaging in those activities once the external incentive is withdrawn. Nevertheless, if a parent instills in their child a sense of personal gratification for accomplishing objectives and a sense of proficiency throughout the educational journey, the child is more inclined to persist in educational tasks due to finding them personally fulfilling and meaningful (Deci et al., 2009).

It was followed by the regularly attend pahina, brigade eskwela, GPTA/ Homeroom meeting, PTC, and other parent-call ups (wt. mean= 3.300, SD=1.449) described as Moderately Involved. Research indicates that parental engagement in education contributes to increased pupil success and enhanced confidence, as stated by the National PTA. The National PTA emphasizes that "family involvement enhances pupil success, irrespective of race/ethnicity, socioeconomic status, or parents' educational level." Parents who have a higher level of comfort in speaking with teachers are more inclined to dedicate their time to volunteering, fundraising, joining in PTA organizations, and engaging in other school activities. Parental volunteers are essential for maintaining after-school activities and promoting academic progress. The involvement of parents facilitates the provision of services by schools that would be difficult to deliver without their cooperation. A notable demonstration of the influence of volunteers may be seen in the Minnesota Reading Corps, where every student receives individualized attention from a tutor to improve their reading abilities. Cultivating connections with parents affords instructors a valuable chance to exert a beneficial impact on their students over the course of several years, spanning from early childhood education to high school completion. Teachers, as the main conduit between parents and the school, have the duty to consistently communicate, seek help when necessary, and actively include parents in the educational process.

The indicator with the lowest mean was I am primarily responsible for making sure that my child is supported to do his or her best in school (wt. mean=2.967, SD=1.402) described as Moderately Involved. This implies that parents unequivocally reassure their children of the support they provide, both in school and in life. Parents can contribute to school activities by assisting with events and functions or by communicating with teachers. Additionally, they can play an active role at home in various ways, such as guiding their children in managing homework and other responsibilities, as well as engaging in conversations about values and attitudes related to education.

Overall, the extent of parents' support towards the academic achievement of pupils in terms of parents as supporter garnered (wt. mean=3.2044, SD=0.0117) described as Moderately Involved. It is commonly recognized that in order for students to achieve their

maximum potential in education, they need the full support of their parents. Increased parental engagement in their children's education correlates with a heightened beneficial influence on the motivation, behavior, and academic performance of the entire class. Promoting parental involvement extends beyond basic politeness; it serves as one of the most powerful methods to create a favorable educational setting for all students. Although parental engagement is not a recent idea, its development in this nation has transitioned from focusing on a son's education and a daughter's dowry to a sincere concern for the education of both sons and daughters.

Over the past few decades, researchers have conducted studies such as the Perry Preschool Project, which was started in 1960 by Sweinhart and Weikart, to evaluate the impact of parental involvement on children's academic and personal accomplishments. This specific study observed a cohort of 123 children who engaged in high-quality early development programs for a duration of two and a half hours, five days per week. In addition, the parents were visited by teachers at their homes on a weekly basis, with each session lasting for ninety minutes.

Table 4 presents the data on the Extent of Parents' Support towards the Academic Achievement of pupils in terms of Parents as Pupils.

Table 4. *Extent of Parents' Support towards the Academic Achievement of pupils in terms of Parents as Pupils*

<i>Parent as Pupil</i>	<i>Indicators</i>	<i>Weighted Mean</i>	<i>Standard Deviation</i>	<i>Qualitative Description</i>
Isip guinikanan, ako naningkamot nga.....				
1. I am primarily responsible for making sure that my child has enough time set aside to do all of his or her school-related work.(Ako ang pina-kresponsable nga maniguro nga ang akong anak naay eksaktong panahon nga gigahin para mabuhat ang tanan niyang angay buluhaton sa eskwelahan.)		3.767	3.506	Strongly Involved
2. My child's teacher(s) hold high expectations for my child; I undergo tutorial and self-study to be able to assist my child. (Ang teacher sa akong anak taas ug gilauman sa kahibalo sa akong anak mao nga ako gatuon pud para matabangan nako ang akong anak.)		3.489	1.300	Strongly Involved
3. I am not confident that I have the full ability to assist child with Math, English, and Science content so I seek help through tutorial, research, and self-study. (Wala akoy eksaktong pagsalig sa akong abilidad para matabangan akong anak sa Math, English, ug Science mao nga ako naningkamot magpatudlo sa uban, magresearch, ug magtuon sa akong kaugalingong paninguha.)		3.478	1.317	Strongly Involved
4. I believe that my child's education today is far more different from mine.(Nagatuo ako nga ang edukasyon karon lahi ra kayo sa katong sa amoa sa una.)		3.433	1.358	Strongly Involved
5. I receive information on what my child should learn and be able to do/understand it myself in order for me to help him/her. (Makadawat ako ug mga impormasyon kung unsa ang angayan nga matun-an sa akong anak ug ako mismo angay nga nakasabot niini aron matabangan nako siya.)		3.356	1.385	Moderately Involved
	Total	3.5225	0.8145	Strongly Involved

Legend: 4.20 – 5.00 – Very Strongly Involved (VSI) | 3.40 – 4.19 – Strongly Involved (SI) | 2.60 – 3.39 – Moderately Involved (MI) | 1.80 – 2.59 – Less Involved or Never (LI) | 1.00 – 1.79 – Not Involved (NI)

As shown in Table 4, the extent of parents' support towards the academic achievement of pupils in terms of parents as pupils revealed that the indicator which got the highest mean was I am primarily responsible for making sure that my child has enough time set aside to do all of his or her school-related work (wt. mean=3.767, SD=3.506, described as Strongly Involved).

These findings suggest that parents in this study had a high level of attentiveness towards their children's study time. Parents who indicated that their children were academically successful displayed an intrusive parenting style, closely monitoring not only their children's schoolwork but also numerous aspects of their lives. This surveillance behavior encompassed vigilance regarding their children's recreational pursuits, familiarity with their social circle, and the imposition of stringent curfew regulations. Parents and children engaged in frequent communication, with parents expressing a strong sense of trust and camaraderie with their children. Although ethnicity plays a significant role in this study, the results are probably relevant to all parents that follow a comparable approach to parenting. Zellman and Waterman (2008) found in their study of white, African American, and Latino parents that the impact of ethnicity and family structure on individual measurements was mostly insignificant.

According to Henderson & Mapp (2002), parent and community involvement activities that are directly related to student learning have a greater influence on academic achievement compared to more broad types of involvement. Furthermore, parent involvement activities may be more effective in enhancing academic achievement when they are centered around specific academic needs. At some point, parents tend to make efforts to learn new things they haven't tried or acquired before, specifically to assist their children and be better equipped to provide help.

It was followed by the indicator My child's teacher(s) hold high expectations for my child; I undergo tutorial and self-study to be able to assist my child (wt. mean= 3.489, SD=.300) described as Strongly Involved. Studies suggest that parents can enhance their children's learning outcomes by actively engaging in their schooling. Parental involvement exerts a greater impact on academic performance than standardized achievement test scores. Some therapies designed to assist parents and improve their parenting abilities go beyond the boundaries of conventional training programs. These interventions involve all the individuals or groups who have a role in a child's

education, such as head teachers, school personnel (including support workers), children, and parents. The fundamental ideology behind this approach is that all these persons play a role in forming the child's self-concept, which is seen as the main factor influencing the child's educational development.

The expectations that parents have for their children's education are strongly connected to their academic achievement in school. Specifically, higher expectations from parents are associated with better grades in English, math, and scientific subjects. Moreover, there exists a strong association between parents who implement regulations inside their household and the scholastic achievement of their offspring (Velez & Jones, 1997). Velez and Jones (2007) conducted interviews with Latino parents and found that there was a significant degree of interaction and involvement between them and their children. Each family reported participating in communal activities, such as attending religious services, playing soccer, and dining out. Parents actively participated in dialogues with their children regarding events and matters in their life, deliberated on educational concerns, and conveyed their aspirations. Every family in the sample highlighted the importance of overseeing and monitoring schoolwork. The homework guidelines include explicit instructions regarding the designated area, time limit, and incentives for completing the assignments. Collectively, every parent in the sample demonstrated elevated ambitions for their children's education.

The indicator with the lowest mean was I receive information on what my child should learn and be able to do/understand it myself in order for me to help him/her (wt. mean=3.356, SD=1.385) and described as Moderately Involved. This implies that some parents engage in self-study to better support their children. The most successful individuals are those who maintain a commitment to learning and personal growth throughout their lives. Parents who demonstrate a love and motivation for acquiring new knowledge and exploring the world tend to cultivate children who inherently value learning. Demonstrating positive learning behavior does not necessarily require a financial investment. Parents can take their children to local places, exploring the environment, local landmarks, and historic sites within their town.

Children are naturally curious in the early stages of life, showing an eagerness to ask questions about the various things around them. To reduce the likelihood that a child may outgrow this curious stage, parents can exemplify that even at their age, they remain curious and fascinated by learning new things (Beverage, 2013). Being willing to learn with enthusiasm and curiosity and allowing your child to enjoy the experience with you, fosters a positive attitude toward learning for your child, and as a bonus, it comes at no cost.

Table 5 presents the data on the Extent of Parents' Support towards the Academic Achievement of pupils in terms of parents as Advocate.

Table 5. *Extent of Parents' Support towards the Academic Achievement of pupils in terms of parents as Advocate*

<i>Parent as Advocate</i>	<i>Indicators</i>	<i>Weighted Mean</i>	<i>Standard Deviation</i>	<i>Qualitative Description</i>
	Isip guinikanan, ako naningkamot nga.....			
	1. I am primarily responsible for making sure that my child understands what is being taught in school. (Ako ang pinaka responsible sa pagsiguro nga nakasabot akong anak kung unsay ginatudlo sa eskwelahan.)	4.045	5.203	Strongly Involved
	2. I believe that parents should be invited to meetings so that I can learn about what is going on in the school (e.g., issues or policies). (Nagatuo ako nga ang mga guinikanan dapat imbitaron sa mga meetings aron nga kami makahibalo kung unsay nahitabo sa eskwelahan.)	3.656	1.325	Strongly Involved
	3. I believe that teachers need to be aware of home problems that may affect my child so they can understand him/her better. (Nagatuo ako nga ang mga maestra/o, kinahanglan makabalo sa mga problema sa panimalay nga posibleng makaapekto sa akong bata para ilang mas masabtan.)	3.611	1.347	Strongly Involved
	4. When my child's school communicates with me it is easy for me to read or understand. (Kung ang eskwelahan makig-komunikar kanako, mas dali nako masabtan.)	3.589	1.271	Strongly Involved
	5. I believe in open communication. ...If there is a question, concern or comment about my child's status, I honestly inform the teacher, principal or guidance counselor to let me know. (Motuo ako sa panag-istoryahay o "opencommunication". Kung ako anaay buot ipangutana bahin sa kahimtang sa akong anak, akong ihangyo sa maestro/principal, o guidance counselor nga pahibal-on ko.)	3.489	1.326	Strongly Involved
		Total	3.678	1.24344
				Strongly Involved

Legend: 4.20 – 5.00 – Very Strongly Involved (VSI) | 3.40 – 4.19 – Strongly Involved (SI) | 2.60 – 3.39 – Moderately Involved (MI) | 1.80 – 2.59 – Less Involved or Never (LI) | 1.00 – 1.79 – Not Involved (NI)

As shown in Table 5, the extent of parents' support towards the academic achievement of pupils in terms of parents as advocate revealed that the indicator I am primarily responsible for making sure that my child understands what is being taught in school (wt. mean=4.045, SD=5.203) described as Strongly Involved. It was followed by I believe that parents should be invited to meetings so that I can learn about what is going on in the school (e.g., issues or policies) (wt. mean=3.656, SD=1.325) described as Strongly Involved. The indicator with the lowest mean was When my child's school communicates with me it is easy for me to read or understand (wt.mean= 3.589, SD=1.271) described as Strongly Involved. Armstrong-Piner (2008) found that parental participation has a greater impact on student

accomplishment compared to socioeconomic position, ethnicity, or the educational level of parents. Hoover-Dempsey (1995) suggests that it is advisable to engage in any type of participation rather than not being involved at all. Additionally, Kroeger (2005) emphasizes that the quality of involvement is more important than the number.

After parents have established a successful motivational strategy to improve academic performance, it is essential for them to actively engage in the learning process. This engagement guarantees that their child acquires the resources and assistance essential for becoming a skilled and effective student in the future. "A child's education starts at birth, experts agree, and the most crucial years of learning actually come in the first six years of a child's life. This means parents hold the key to a child's future academic success" (Smith, 2011).

Parents and community people can play a crucial role as supporters and advocates for their children's education by participating in site-based school restructuring. The restructuring of schools with the aim of cultivating partnerships among parents, families, communities, and schools mostly centers around the organizational framework. Modifying activities, forging new partnerships, and employing inventive ideas are methods by which schools might reorganize to promote parent and community engagement in this capacity.

The parents' support towards the academic progress of kids, namely as advocates, was found to have a total weighted mean of 3.678 and a standard deviation of 1.24344, indicating a strong level of involvement. Parental engagement is vital for the academic achievement of students. By engaging in collaboration with parents, teachers gain the supplementary assistance needed to aid difficult students in enhancing their academic achievement. In addition, parents cultivate a lifetime passion for learning in each student, resulting in more engaged and passionate students. Teachers can engage parents as active collaborators in education by promoting communication, supporting parental involvement in the classroom, and offering opportunities for home-based enrichment.

Parents can exert a substantial academic influence on their child's life by regularly reading together, ensuring that talks between parent and child are filled with advanced language, and making use of resources accessible within their communities (Smith, 2011). Although the Family Engagement Act does not have the required parliamentary support, it has motivated the Department of Education to begin creating several programs and measures to facilitate parental involvement. The U.S. Department of Education has implemented a dual capacity framework with the goal of augmenting parental engagement. The significant focus on investigating the impact of parental involvement on student accomplishment and creating initiatives to enhance involvement highlights the crucial role of parental engagement in the educational process.

Table 6 presents the data on the Extent of Parents' Support towards the Academic Achievement of pupils in terms of parents as Decision Maker.

Table 6. *Extent of Parents' Support towards the Academic Achievement of pupils in terms of parents as Decision Maker*

<i>Parent as Decision Maker</i>	<i>Indicators</i>	<i>Weighted Mean</i>	<i>Standard Deviation</i>	<i>Qualitative Description</i>
Isip guinikanan, ako naningkamot nga.....				
	1. I decide about the extra-curricular activities and fund-raising projects that my child joins at school. (Ako ang ga-desisyon kung unsa nga kalihokan ug "fund-raising project" ang apilan sa akong anak.)	3.622	1.320	Strongly Involved
	2. If I think that my suggestion is right, I do my part to be able to explain it so that other teachers and parents would understand and vote with me. (Kung nakabalo ko nga ang akong sugyot tama, akong buhaton akong katungod nga mag-explain para masabtan ko sa mga guinikanan ug maestro aron mo-pabor sa akoo.)	3.622	1.277	Strongly Involved
	3. I believe that for me to be able to exercise my right in the school of my child, I must do my responsibilities as a parent also. (Nagatuo ako nga para akong makuha ang akong katungod sa pagpaeskwela sa akong anak, kinahanglan ako pud buhaton ang akong responsibilidad isip guinikanan.)	3.611	1.313	Strongly Involved
	4. I participate in the school meetings so that I may be able to voice out my decision about school programs and policies.(Nagaapil ako sa mga "meetings" sa eskwelahan aron akong maipahayag akong desisyon sa mga programa ug polisiya sa eskwelahan.)	3.533	1.283	Strongly Involved
	5. I decide about the school and teacher-adviser that my child must be attending to.(Ako ang gahukom kung asa nga eskwelahan ug kung kinsa nga maestra ang sa akong anak.)	3.511	1.318	Strongly Involved
	Total	3.5798	0.0178	Strongly Involved

Legend: 4.20 – 5.00 – Very Strongly Involved (VSI) | 3.40 – 4.19 – Strongly Involved (SI) | 2.60 – 3.39 – Moderately Involved (MI) | 1.80 – 2.59 – Less Involved or Never (LI) | 1.00 – 1.79 – Not Involved (NI)

As shown in Table 6, the extent of parents' support towards the academic achievement of pupils in terms of parents as decision maker revealed that the indicator with the highest mean was I decide about the extra-curricular activities and fund-raising projects that my child joins at school (wt. mean=3.622, SD=.320) and If I think that my suggestion is right, I do my part to be able to explain it so that other teachers and parents would understand and vote with me (wt. mean=3.622, SD=1.277) both described as Strongly Involved. It was followed by the indicator I believe that for me to be able to exercise my right in the school of my child, I must do my responsibilities as a parent also (wt. mean=3.611, SD=1.313) described as Strongly Involved. The indicator with the lowest mean was I participate in the school meetings so that I may be able to voice out my decision about school programs and policies (wt. mean=3.51, SD=1.318) described as Strongly Involved. To emphasize their significance, Ediger (2008) recommended conducting parent-teacher conferences

at least twice during the school year. He further explained that the purpose of these meetings is to provide an opportunity for teachers and parents to collaborate for the benefit of the child, which may involve making decisions about implementing projects or launching fundraising activities to enhance the school. According to Jordan et al. (2001), parental involvement initiatives should move away from the school-centered paradigm where parents merely support school-determined agendas. Instead, they should adopt a new paradigm in which parents take on roles as decision-makers and leaders.

Overall, the extent of parents’ support towards the academic achievement of pupils in terms of parents as decision maker got a total of weighted mean=3.5798 and SD=0.0178 described as Strongly Involved.

Table 7 presents the data on the Extent of Parents’ Support towards the Academic Achievement of pupils in terms of parents as Volunteer/ Professional.

Table 7. Extent of Parents’ Support towards the Academic Achievement of pupils in terms of parents as Volunteer/ Professional

Indicators	Weighted Mean	Standard Deviation	Qualitative Description
<i>Parent as Professional Volunteer</i>			
Isip guinikanan, ako naningkamot nga.....			
1. I volunteer to get information about services to support my child’s learning and behavior needs and enhance his or her talents (tutoring, mentoring, camps, etc). (Ako ga-boluntaryo nga makakuha ug impormasyon para makasuporta sa pagtuon ug gawi sa akong anak ug mapalambo ang iyang talent sama sa “tutoring”, “mentoring”, ug uban pa.)	3.644	1.292	Strongly Involved
2. I am the one who voluntarily assists my child’s schooling. (Ako ang ga-boluntaryo nga motabang sa pagtuon sa akong anak.)	3.598	1.253	Strongly Involved
3. I do not wait for the teacher/s to follow-up; I usually submit myself to attend meetings, pahina, programs, etc. (Dili na ako gahulat sa mga maestro para mag-follow-up. Kasagaran, ako ang ga-boluntaryo nga moapil ug meeting, pahina, programa, ug uban pa.)	3.589	1.253	Strongly Involved
4. I am primarily responsible for ensuring good communication between home and school; hence, I volunteer to inquire by asking the teacher. (Ako ang responsable para masiguro ang maayong kumonikasyon sa eskwelahan ug panimalay busa ako ga-boluntaryo pinaagi sa pagpangutana sa maestro.)	3.544	1.300	Strongly Involved
5. I am not confident with my ability to support my child’s learning at home so I volunteer to seek help or enroll short courses. (Dili igo ang akong pagsalig sa akong abilidad para suportahan ang pagtuon sa akong anak sa balay mao nga boluntaryo akong mangayo ug tabang sa uban o mag-enroll ug programa/kurso.)	3.456	1.400	Strongly Involved
	Total	3.5662	0.0403
			Strongly Involved

Legend: 4.20 – 5.00 – Very Strongly Involved (VSI) | 3.40 – 4.19 – Strongly Involved (SI) | 2.60 – 3.39 – Moderately Involved (MI) | 1.80 – 2.59 – Less Involved or Never (LI) | 1.00 – 1.79 – Not Involved (NI)

As shown in Table 7, the extent of parents’ support towards the academic achievement of pupils in terms of parents as volunteer/ professional revealed that the indicator with the highest mean was I volunteer to get information about services to support my child’s learning and behavior needs and enhance his or her talents (tutoring, mentoring, camps, etc) (wt. mean=3.644, SD=1.292) described as Strongly Involved. This suggests that regardless of governmental rules, certain parents have consistently taken an active role in fostering their children's growth and academic progress. This impromptu involvement has materialized in diverse manifestations, such as implementing 'effective parenting' at home throughout the early childhood stage, establishing a strong base of abilities, principles, outlooks, and self-perception. Additionally, it entails physically going to the school to collect relevant information and establish favorable connections, engaging in conversations with teachers to remain informed about the child's advancement or tackle developing concerns, and participating more extensively in the actual undertakings and administration of the school.

It was followed by the indicator I am the one who voluntarily assists my child’s schooling (wt. mean=3.598 SD=1.253) described as Strongly Involved. The voluntary participation of numerous parents is seen as a valuable contribution to the educational advancement of children, and initiatives to augment the participation of all parents are currently prevalent. Parents that champion their children's education spend additional time to school projects, provide assistance with homework, and actively participate as volunteers at schools. As stated in "A New Wave of Evidence," a publication by the National Center for Family & Community Connections with Schools, children with parents who possess these qualities demonstrate superior performance on standardized tests, attain higher grades, derive greater satisfaction from their educational experience, cultivate enhanced social abilities, and exhibit a greater likelihood of pursuing higher education. An article published in the 2010 issue of Educational Psychology: An International Journal of Experimental Educational Psychology similarly found a direct relationship between student engagement and motivation, and the level of parental involvement. Considering the multitude of advantages associated with parental engagement, it is incumbent upon teachers to give it precedence.

The indicator with the lowest mean was I am not confident with my ability to support my child's learning at home so I volunteer to seek help or enrol short courses (wt. mean=3.456, SD=1.400) described as Strongly Involved. With the introduction of DepEd Order No. 41, s. 2012, parents are no longer obligated to make compulsory payments for all school fees, as they are now purely voluntary.

This means that providing assistance or paying school fees as presented in the school is no longer a mandatory requirement for parents. However, the limited enthusiasm for volunteerism among some parents is evidently affecting their children's motivation in school. This could be attributed to social pressure and personal pride that arise when their attention is called for follow-up by the person in charge of collection, although it is not compulsory.

Overall, the extent of parents' support towards the academic achievement of pupils in terms of parents as volunteer/ professional got a total mean=3.5662 and SD=0.0403 described as Strongly Involved. Parents should be actively engaged and included in all program activities, even to the extent of spending their money, as long as they are acknowledged, valued, and consulted, particularly in financial matters. They should play a role in decision-making, not merely being instructed to pay or contribute by others. Therefore, parents appreciate being kept informed about the school's financial matters. The transparency implemented by the school will enhance trust and confidence, encouraging them to provide further support for all school programs and activities.

DepEd Memorandum No. 192, s. 2009 encourages parents to offer voluntary assistance through a spirit of volunteerism to motivate pupils to attend school, stay engaged, and develop their capacities. This approach could be seen as a temporary solution to the challenges faced by public schools, primarily attributed to the government's insufficient budget allocation for education (Serillano, 2009).

Table 8 presents the data on the Extent of Parents' Support towards the Academic Achievement of pupils in terms of parents as Home Activities Teacher.

Table 8. *Extent of Parents' Support towards the Academic Achievement of pupils in terms of parents as Home Activities Teacher*

<i>Parent as Home Activities Teacher</i>	<i>Indicators</i>	<i>Weighted Mean</i>	<i>Standard Deviation</i>	<i>Qualitative Description</i>
Isip guinikanan, ako naningkamot nga.....				
1.	I make sure that my child reviews and corrects school-related work. (Akong gipaniguro nga ang akong anak ga-review sa iyang mga bulohaton sa eskwelahan.)	3.733	1.296	Strongly Involved
2.	I emphasize to my child about the importance of learning to do things independently at home. (Akong gipasabot sa akong anak ang importansya sa pagtuon nga buhaton ang iyang trabaho sa eskwelahan sa among panimalay nga siya lamang.)	3.511	1.220	Strongly Involved
3.	I am confident with my ability to understand the Math, English, Science content being taught in my child's classes. (Nagasalig ako sa akong abilidad nga makasabot sa Math, English, Science nga gitudlo sa akong anak sa ilang klase.)	3.489	1.229	Strongly Involved
4.	I help my child make his/her assignments, projects at home. (Akong gatabangan ang akong anak sa paghimo sa iyang assignment ug proyekto sa balay.)	3.478	1.256	Strongly Involved
5.	I seek help from other people to be able to help my child at home. (Mangita ako'g tabang sa ubang tawo para matabangan ang akong anak sa iyang leksyon sa among balay.)	3.200	1.384	Moderately Involved
Total		3.4822	0.0504	Strongly Involved

Legend: 4.20 – 5.00 – Very Strongly Involved (VSI) | 3.40 – 4.19 – Strongly Involved (SI) | 2.60 – 3.39 – Moderately Involved (MI) | 1.80 – 2.59 – Less Involved or Never (LI) | 1.00 – 1.79 – Not Involved (NI)

As shown in Table 8, the extent of parents' support towards the academic achievement of pupils in terms of parents as home activities teacher revealed that the indicator I make sure that my child reviews and corrects school-related work (wt. mean=3.200, SD=1.384) described as Moderately Involved. It was followed by I emphasize to my child about the importance of learning to do things independently at home (wt. mean=3.511, SD=1.220) described as Strongly Involved. The indicator with the lowest mean was I seek help from other people to be able to help my child at home (wt.mean=3.200, SD=1.384) described as Moderately Involved.

According to the research conducted by Hafiz Muhammad Waqas Rafiq et al. (2013), parents indeed serve as the initial educators of their children. Parents are considered partners in their children's educational journey. The study highlights that Parental involvement encompasses various activities, such as assisting children in reading, motivating them to complete their homework autonomously, overseeing their activities both inside and outside the home, and offering coaching services to enhance their learning in different subjects. These actions have a significant influence on pupils' educational outcomes.

Overall, the extent of parents' support towards the academic achievement of pupils in terms of parents as home activities teacher got a total weighted man=3.4822 and SD=0.0504 described as Strongly Involved. The research conducted by Milad Khajehpoura and Sayid Dabbagh Ghazvinia (n.d.) found that parents engaged in more home-related activities, such as checking their child's programming, discussing classroom topics, lessons, and friendships at home, or participating in educational activities outside of school, had children who performed better academically and achieved higher grades.

Seginer (2006) and Lee (2006) have asserted that school involvement includes activities like attending parent-teacher conferences, volunteering, and participating in programs and extracurricular events. On the other hand, home involvement takes the form of assisting with homework, managing time, and engaging in educational discussions.

Academic Achievement of Pupils in Araling Panlipunan

Table 9 shows the Academic Achievement of Pupils in Araling Panlipunan.

Table 9. *Academic Achievement of Pupils in Araling Panlipunan, N=90*

<i>Grading Scale</i>	<i>Qualitative Description</i>	<i>Frequency Count</i>	<i>Percentage</i>
90-100	Outstanding	2	2.22
85-89	Very Satisfactory	19	21.11
80 – 84	Satisfactory	52	57.78
75-79	Fairly Satisfactory	17	18.89
Below 75	Did not meet Expectations	0	0

Table 9 reveals that 52 out of 90 pupils have a grading scale from 80-84 classified as Satisfactory, 19 out of 90 have grades between 85-89 with Very satisfactory status, 17 out of 90 have grades that ranges from 75-79 with a description of fairly satisfactory and only 2 out of 90 have grades in Araling Panlipunan of 90-100 with outstanding performance. This result shows that more than 50% of the respondents have Satisfactory rating in the first quarter of Araling Panlipunan. This implies that pupils need more focus on their studies and follow up from their parents on their study habits is necessary.

This suggests that the academic performance and adaptation of students are influenced by a range of individuals, processes, and institutions. Parents, extended family, peer groups, local influences, schools, and other entities, such as churches and clubs, collectively shape children's development in terms of personal growth and civic responsibility. The children, with their distinct capabilities, dispositions, and tendencies, exert significant influence in molding and modifying their conduct, ambitions, and accomplishments.

Parental engagement in education is crucial. Pupils, regardless of their income or background, who have parents that are actively involved, are more inclined to attain higher grades and test scores, maintain regular attendance at school, display superior social skills, demonstrate improved behavior, and adjust well to the school environment. Research indicates that children perform better in school when parents maintain frequent communication with teachers and actively engage in school-related activities. Moreover, parents also have a say in decisions that may impact their child's education.

Initial research frequently demonstrated significant positive connections between parental engagement in schools and student academic advancement, suggesting that active participation in school activities contributed to this success. Nevertheless, the level of parental engagement is significantly correlated with the socio-economic position, which, in turn, has an even stronger association with student advancement (Charles, Desforges, and Abouchaar, 2003).

Parental engagement exerts a substantial beneficial influence on student academic performance. Research indicates that parental participation significantly impacts academic attainment. In fact, it has been proposed that schools would have to allocate an additional \$1000 per student in order to obtain similar learning outcomes without parental involvement (Westmoreland, Rosenberg, Lopez, & Weiss, 2009). Parental participation is the primary factor that has the greatest impact on promoting better levels of accomplishment. Curiously, the University of New Hampshire found that when schools provided more resources for students, parents seemed to reduce their levels of engagement. This might potentially undermine the desired impact of greater resources.

Test for significant relationship between the Extent of Parents' Support towards the Academic Achievement of pupils in terms of parents as: Communicator, Supporter, Pupil, Advocate, Decision Maker, Volunteer, and Acting as Home Teacher and the Academic Achievement of Pupils

Table 10 displays the relationship between the Extent of Parents' Support towards the Academic Achievement of pupils in terms of parents as: Communicator, Supporter, Pupil, Advocate, Decision Maker, Volunteer, and Acting as Home Teacher and the Academic Achievement of Pupils

Table 10. *Test for Significant Relationship between Extent of Parents' Support towards the Academic Achievement of pupils in terms of parents as: Communicator, Supporter, Pupil, Advocate, Decision Maker, Volunteer, and Acting as Home Teacher and the Academic Achievement of Pupils*

<i>Indicators</i>	<i>r</i>	<i>p-value</i>	<i>Remarks</i>
1. Communicator	0.176	0.098	Not significant
2. Supporter	0.030	0.782	Not Significant
3. Pupil	-0.090	0.397	Not Significant
4. Advocate	0.007	0.945	Not Significant
5. Decision Maker	-0.045	0.673	Not Significant
6. Volunteer	0.045	0.674	Not Significant
7. Home Teacher	-0.010	0.924	Not Significant

Level of Significance: $\alpha=0.05$

Table 10 reveals the Pearson r values and the p-values of the data. Pearson r tells us the strength of the relationship of the variables and the p-values indicate the basis whether to reject or accept the null hypothesis when compared with the level of significance. The data

expose that the p-values are all greater than the level of significance which is set at $\alpha=0.05$ hence, not one of the indicators is significant. This means that there is no significant relationship between the extent of parents' support towards the academic achievement of pupils in terms of parents as: communicator, supporter, pupil, advocator, decision maker, volunteer, and acting as home teacher and the academic achievement of pupils. Hence, the null hypothesis which states that There is no significant relationship between the extent of parental support towards their child and the pupils' academic achievement is not rejected.

Desforges and Abouchaar (2003) conducted early research on the topic, which produced a range of contradictory and contradicting findings. This supports the conclusion. Several studies have shown that parental participation does not have any influence on pupil achievement or adjustment, while others have discovered notable positive impacts. In contrast, certain studies have found a negative correlation, indicating that parental participation may decrease student achievement in specific situations. The differences are explicable by the fact that various researchers used various definitions of parental participation. Some individuals regarded it as equivalent to 'exemplary parenting' within the household, whereas others characterized it as 'communicating with educators,' and yet others perceived it as comprehensive involvement in school activities and administration.

This discovery runs counter to a study by Velez & Jones (2007) that emphasized how strong a foundation for academic success the relationship between parents and children provides. Greater interpersonal connections, specifically with educational concerns, lead to elevated academic performance. The evidence for this research is indisputable: when schools and families work together to enhance learning, children are more likely to achieve success not only in school but also in all aspects of life (Wherry, 2000).

According to Johnston (2008), students whose families were engaged in school activities were more likely to have higher ambitions for their schooling and future professions. These students had a higher propensity to establish career objectives in scientific, technological, and professional domains. High school students who had parents active in their education showed a greater inclination towards enrolling in advanced courses and a better dedication to lifetime learning in comparison to those whose parents were not involved. Adolescents exhibited a decline in instances of crime, alcohol usage, drug use, and other anti-social activities when there was an increase in parental participation in schooling. This suggests a tendency to avoid engaging in high-risk behaviors.

In addition, he delineated the advantages for both the school and community, encompassing enhanced teacher morale, elevated evaluations of instructors by parents, augmented support from families, heightened pupil success, and improved reputations within the neighborhood. It is crucial to acknowledge that the advantages of engaging parents extend beyond early childhood; there are substantial benefits at all stages and academic levels. Adolescents in junior and senior high school who had parents who stayed engaged had smoother transitions, sustained the excellence of their work, and formed practical aspirations for their future.

Upon closer examination of the anomalies in early studies, it becomes apparent that there was a clear lack of sophistication in assessing correlation coefficients. A common observation is that there is a negative correlation between the frequency of parents communicating with instructors regarding their child's conduct and progress and the outcomes of these interactions. Research has indicated a negative correlation between the frequency of parent-teacher communication and the academic success of their children. Based on this premise, it was determined that parental participation had a negative impact on student advancement. Nevertheless, the inquiry arises: which is the underlying factor, and which is the resultant outcome? It is often understood that parents should engage in more communication with instructors when a problem arises. Conversation is a reaction to the problem, not its cause. However, this is not the complete story. Parental participation can be measured by how much parents talk to teachers about their child's growth. It reminds us of that parental involvement and success are likely not linear (doubling parental involvement would not double achievement) and include both proactive and reactive factors. Parents are engaged enough based on their perception (Desforges and Abouchaar, 2003).

Conclusions

The study drew the following conclusions: Parents generally rated the extent of their support toward the academic achievement of pupils as "Strongly Involved." Therefore, parents in Kitaotao III, Division of Bukidnon, were highly supportive and actively engaged in their children's education.

The pupils in Kitaotao III, Division of Bukidnon, require additional attention to their studies, and parental follow-up on their study habits is deemed necessary.

There was no significant relationship found between the extent of parental support for their children and the academic achievement of the pupils.

Parents can maintain their robust participation in school programs, activities, and projects (PAPs). They should consistently provide support for the academic achievement of their children, taking on roles such as Communicator, Supporter, Pupil, Advocate, Decision Maker, Volunteer, Acting as Home Teacher, and Collaborator, especially during the ongoing COVID-19 Pandemic when they act as partners with teachers to facilitate the pupil's education in the absence of face-to-face instruction.

Teachers should devise more engaging strategies to inspire pupils to approach their studies with dedication, aiming to elevate satisfactory academic achievements to very satisfactory or even outstanding levels.

School administrators should implement additional programs and strategies to ensure the continuous and strong involvement of parents

as a support system for school children and school PAPs.

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